

NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION AND ITS REFLECTION IN LITERARY DISCOURSE

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Abstract. Nonverbal communication refers to the use of body language, facial expressions, and other nonverbal cues to convey meaning. In literary discourse, nonverbal communication can be reflected through the use of descriptive language and imagery that conveys emotions and actions without explicitly stating them. Therefore, it is important to use nonverbal communication in literary discourse. For that reason, the article presents the investigation of non-verbal communication and its reflection in literary discourse.

Keywords: literature, communication, nonverbal communication, discourse, expression, reflection.

Nonverbal communication plays a significant role in literature as it helps authors to convey emotions, actions, and cultural norms. By using descriptive language and imagery, authors can paint a vivid picture of their characters' physical reactions and body language, which provides insight into their thoughts and feelings [6]. This, in turn, creates depth and complexity in their characters, settings, and themes. In other words, nonverbal communication is an integral part of literary discourse that adds depth and complexity to characters, settings, and themes. By paying attention to the nonverbal cues in literature, readers can gain a richer understanding of the story's meaning and significance.

Nonverbal communication also reflects cultural norms and values in literature. It helps readers to understand the complex cultural norms of different societies and how they affect the behavior of the characters. By using nonverbal cues such as body language and facial expressions, authors can reveal the strict gender roles and expectations of different societies.

Ch.Darwin is considered a pioneer in the study of nonverbal communication. In his work “The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals” (1872) the foundations of a scientific approach to the study of emotions and ways of their bodily representation were laid [3].

In 1952, the American anthropologist R.Birdwhistell introduced the concept of “kinesics” and developed a grammar of nonverbal behavior by analogy with linguistics [1].

Currently, body movements, facial expressions and gestures are being studied by representatives of such areas of nonverbal semiotics as auscultation, haptics, olfaction, proxemics, phonemics, phonation, kinesics [5].

A primary function of nonverbal communication is to convey meaning by reinforcing, substituting for, or contradicting verbal communication. Nonverbal communication is also used to influence others and regulate conversational flow. Perhaps even more important are the ways in which nonverbal communication functions as a central part of relational communication and identity expression.

For example, a character's posture or facial expression can reveal their mood or attitude towards a situation. In Ernest Hemingway's "The Old Man and the Sea," the protagonist's physical struggles with the marlin he catches reflect his determination and perseverance.

Nonverbal communication can also reflect cultural norms and values in literature. In China

Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, the use of nonverbal cues such as body language and facial expressions reveals the complex cultural norms of the Igbo people in Nigeria. The protagonist Okonkwo's posture, gestures, and facial expressions reflect his adherence to the strict gender roles and expectations of his society.

For example, in F. Scott Fitzgerald's *The Great Gatsby*, the protagonist Jay Gatsby's nervous gestures and facial expressions reveal his anxiety and insecurity when he is around Daisy Buchanan. Similarly, in Ernest Hemingway's *The Old Man and the Sea*, the old fisherman's body language and physical exhaustion convey his determination and resilience in the face of adversity.

Nonverbal communication influences others, as it is a key component of deception and can be used to assert dominance or to engage in compliance gaining.

Nonverbal communication regulates conversational flow, as it provides important cues that signal the beginning and end of conversational turns and facilitates the beginning and end of an interaction.

Conclusion. Overall, Nonverbal communication is used extensively in literature to convey emotions, actions, and cultural norms. Authors use descriptive language and imagery to paint a vivid picture of their characters' physical reactions and body language, which provides insight into their thoughts and feelings. That's why, nonverbal communication is an essential tool for authors to create an immersive and authentic reading experience that resonates with their audience. It helps readers to connect with the characters on a deeper level and understand their motivations and behaviors. Therefore, authors must pay close attention to nonverbal cues when writing their stories to make them more compelling and engaging for their readers.

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